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ON INTERRELATIONS BETWEEN GRADUONYMY AND ANTONYMY

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Annotation. *The article deals with interrelations and differences between graduonymy and antonymy, which are two types of lexical-semantic relationships and it serves for the clearly understanding these two phenomena in the language system.*

Key words: *graduonymy, antonymy, gradual antonymy, converse pairs, polar antonyms, parallel antonyms.*

The phenomenon of antonymy or the meaning of contradiction has a special place in the history of linguistics as a necessary form of semantic relations. There are some confusions that are still waiting to be resolved in the field of semantic relations, for example, considering antonymy as a form of synonymy. However, synonymy and antonymy are in different types of semantic relations and have been well studied in the world, especially in the Uzbek linguistics. For example, issues of antonymy such as converseness, additivity, antonyms with "implicit gradation" have been studied. Also, in the study of O. Bozorov dedicated to gradation, there is brief information about the relation of antonymy with graduonymy [1]. The author of the article "On Antonymy in English" In Seok Yang divides antonyms into two categories [2]. On this basis, we can form a graduonymic series, that is, the poles consist of antonyms, and when both words are considered antonyms we pay attention to the analysis of antonyms that can form a graduonymic series, not mutually, but separately. According to English scholars, antonyms can have *gradational*, i.e., *comparative* and *superlative* degrees, while *complementary* and *converse* pairs have no degrees. Taking this into account, the idea arises that *gradable antonyms* can form a graduonymic series, that is, there can be no intervening words between *single-married*. By putting the word normal between *big-small* antonyms, it is possible to see that both antonyms are graded on the basis of connotativeness. In order to respond to another point in the above-mentioned article, it is appropriate to consider graduonymic relationships based on antonyms in English.

Antonyms are separated according to the answers to the questions given to the pair. The main reason for the division of antonyms into these groups is that they depend on the answer given to the interrogative sentence in the form "Hov-Adj - -". Since polar and parallel antonyms can be answered using both antonyms, they are assumed to be neutralizable, as demonstrated by the following examples: (1) a. *How old is he? How young is he?* (2) a. *He's 60 years old/*young.* b. *He's 30 years old/*young.* c. *He's one day old/*young.* (3) a. *He's very young/*old.* b. *He's as young/*old as she is* [4]. Of the answers to these questions, all the previous answers in (2) are valid, except for *young*. So, the word "old" can be considered here as an unmarked member of the *old/young* antonym pairs. It should also be noted that the presence of sentences that continue the answers in (3) ensures that the answer is complete. For example, "he is two years old/*young". Considering the pragmatic basis of pairs of neutralizing antonyms, the author notes that there is no sharp boundary between the pairs in the age scale of the antonyms *old* and *young*. He illustrates how old age starts from youth and continues from youth to old age in the following diagram (diagram taken from In-Seok Yang. On antonymy in English. Language and linguistics. Volume 19, p. 90):

Continuum of age *young*↔*old*

0 Start terminus 0 → → → → → → → → → → → → → → → → boundary

Now, if we come to the question of the direct connection of antonymy with graduonymy, graduonymy is also related to antonymy as a separate linguistic phenomenon that combines synonymy and antonymy. Consequently, as the two poles and limits of the graduonymic series gradually reach the level of contradiction, this is also an example of antonymy in some sense. At the same time, while analyzing the pairs that the scientist called neutralizing antonyms, we came to the conclusion that in most cases such antonyms can have a graduonymic series, and we present the location of these pairs in the graduonymic series below:

Continuum of age *young-old*

0 *newborn* → *baby* → *infant* → *toddler* → *child* → *youngster* → *teenager* → *adult* → *oldster*

Start terminus

0 → → → → → → → → → → → → → → → → 100

A similar line can be observed in the Uzbek language:

ninni ~ chaqaloq ~ go'dak ~ bola ~ bolakay ~ o'smir ~ o'spirin ~ yigit ~ erkak ~ amaki ~ chol

This series is based not only on age, but also on the basis of gender (male) priority, and the opposite (female) chain can be expressed as follows:

ninni ~ chaqaloq ~ go 'dak ~ bola ~ qizaloq ~ o 'smir qiz ~ o 'spirin qiz ~ qiz ~ juvon ~ opa ~ ayol ~ xola ~ kampir ~ momo...

The underlined words in this line indicate the (extreme) relativity of the units, the changeable and conversive character, and even the contextual-connotative coloring (like dialect, individuality, uniqueness, slang...) presents. This once again proves that the graduonymic chains consisting of antonyms of different groups are not only open, but also have a transpositional, conversive and even temporal nature of their (series) members.

As we said above, the antonymic units are sometimes **How+adj...?** understood by a query and answered by a corresponding unit. For example, to separate units from this line a) *How happy is he/she?* b) *How unhappy is he/she?* asking questions like:

A. *He/She is contented.*

He/She is grateful.

He/She is glad.

He/She is pleased.

B. *He/She is sad.*

He/She is unfortunate.

He/She is sorrowful.

He/She is distressed.

He/She is upset.

For making gradual lines through these samples we can see followings:

Pic. 1. Gradual series of units on the question *How happy is he/she?*

A relationship of relative increase (intensification)/decrease (neutralization) can be seen among the units under the meaning "happiness" in the row. A similar relationship can be observed in the following line:

Pic. 2. Gradual series of units on the question *How unhappy is he/she?*

It can be seen that the lexical units arranged along this line undergo relative gradual change (increase/decrease) to each other which gives rise to graduonymy. By aligning the above lines into one general graduonymic series, it becomes possible to identify antonymic units, more precisely, to visualize the place and position of antonymic pairs in the gradation series:

Pic. 3. The line of the units grading on the seme *happiness/unhappiness*

On the basis of the above chain, the two extremes (poles) of the gradual series show a contradiction: *happy-unhappy*. *happy* ~ ... units between *unhappy* polar antonyms are also distinguished by the fact that they form a specific (partial) conflict: *joyful-distressed, pleased-unfortunate, glad-sad, grateful-sorrowful, contented-upset...* These antonymic pairs of a complementary nature certainly represent an increase in polar antonymy (there is also a case for viewing this type of conflict as contextual antonymy).

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